

TERNARY SMIRNOV WORDS AND GENERATING FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

We demonstrate that enumeration problems related to words with neighbouring letters being always different (Smirnov words) are most efficiently done using generating functions.

– *Dedicated to Robert Tichy on the occasion of his 60th birthday.*

1. Introduction

Smirnov words [1] are characterized by the property that the words $x_1 \dots x_n$ must satisfy the condition that $x_i \neq x_{i+1}$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n - 1$. To obtain generating functions for them is a well known process [1]; for a recent application of the principle, the reader is referred to [2].

Koshy and Grimaldi [3] treated several enumerations around *ternary* (Smirnov) words (an alphabet with 3 letters is underlying) in an elementary fashion, which involves long computations. The aim of the present note is to show how Smirnov words and generating functions get such results in a painless way. Generalizations to more than 3 letters and additional parameters are immanent.

Many results may be expressed by Jacobsthal and Jacobsthal-Lucas numbers

$$J_n = \frac{2^n - (-1)^n}{3} \quad \text{and} \quad j_n = 2^n + (-1)^n.$$

This is not essential, and is always possible, since one can replace 2^n by $J_{n+1} + J_n$ and $(-1)^n$ by $J_{n+1} - 2J_n$.

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2. Ternary Smirnov Words Starting and Ending With the Letter 0

We assume that the 3 letters are 0, 1, 2 and set up generating functions $f_i(z)$ via the system

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z) &= z + zf_1(z) + zf_2(z), \\ f_1(z) &= zf_0(z) + zf_2(z), \\ f_2(z) &= zf_0(z) + zf_1(z). \end{aligned}$$

This system is inspired by random walks, and describes how a new letter is appended, which must be different from the previous one. The letter z marks the letters. The functions $f_i(z)$ count Smirnov words starting with 0 and ending with i . In [3] the main interest was in $f_0(z)$, but the other two are easy as well. The solutions are:

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z) &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{1}{1-2z} - \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{1+z}, \\ f_1(z) = f_2(z) &= -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{1}{1-2z} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{1+z}, \\ f_0(z) + f_1(z) + f_2(z) &= -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1-2z}. \end{aligned}$$

Reading off the coefficient of z^n , we find for $n \geq 1$:

$$[z^n]f_0(z) = \frac{1}{6}2^n - \frac{2}{3}(-1)^n = 2J_{n-2}, \quad [z^n]f_1(z) = \frac{1}{6}2^n + \frac{1}{3}(-1)^n = J_{n-1}.$$

In total, we get of course 2^{n-1} Smirnov words of length n , starting with 0.

Corollary 1 of [3] gives J_{n-2} for the number of Smirnov words, starting with 01 and ending with 0. This follows without computation from the symmetry of such words having the second letter equal to 1 resp. 2.

3. Ternary Smirnov Words Starting and Ending With the Letter 0 – Counting the Letters 0

We can use essentially the same equations, but now using a second variable u , counting the numbers 0:

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z, u) &= zu + zf_1(z, u) + zf_2(z, u), \\ f_1(z, u) &= zuf_0(z, u) + zf_2(z, u), \\ f_2(z, u) &= zuf_0(z) + zf_1(z, u). \end{aligned}$$

We find

$$f_0(z, u) = \frac{zu(1-z)}{1-z-2z^2u} = \frac{zu}{1-\frac{2z^2}{1-z}u}.$$

Therefore (for $n \geq 2$ and $k \geq 2$)

$$[u^k]f_0(z, u) = 2^{k-1} \frac{z^{2k-1}}{(1-z)^{k-1}},$$

and

$$[z^n u^k]f_0(z, u) = [z^n]2^{k-1} \frac{z^{2k-1}}{(1-z)^{k-1}} = [z^{n+1-2k}] \frac{2^{k-1}}{(1-z)^{k-1}} = 2^{k-1} \binom{n-1-k}{k-2}.$$

The total number of letters 0 in Smirnov words of length n is given via $\frac{\partial}{\partial u} f_0(z, 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned} [z^n] & \left(\frac{1}{18} \frac{1}{(1-2z)^2} + \frac{5}{54} \frac{1}{1-2z} - \frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{(1+z)^2} + \frac{8}{27} \frac{1}{1+z} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{18}(n+1)2^n + \frac{5}{54}2^n - \frac{4}{9}(n+1)(-1)^n + \frac{8}{27}(-1)^n \\ &= \frac{1}{18}n2^n + \frac{4}{27}2^n - \frac{4}{9}n(-1)^n - \frac{4}{27}(-1)^n. \end{aligned}$$

Analogous computations are as follows:

$$f_1(z, u) = \frac{z^2u^2}{1-z-2z^2u} = \frac{z^2u^2}{1-z} \frac{1}{1-\frac{2z^2}{1-z}u},$$

and

$$[u^k]f_1(z, u) = \frac{z^2}{1-z} [u^{k-2}] \frac{1}{1-\frac{2z^2}{1-z}u} = 2^{k-2} \frac{z^{2k-2}}{(1-z)^{k-1}},$$

and

$$[z^n u^k]f_1(z, u) = 2^{k-2} [z^{n+2-2k}] \frac{1}{(1-z)^{k-1}} = 2^{k-2} \binom{n-k}{k-2}.$$

Furthermore,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u} f_1(z, 1) = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{18} \frac{1}{(1-2z)^2} + \frac{4}{27} \frac{1}{1-2z} + \frac{2}{9} \frac{1}{(1+z)^2} + \frac{2}{27} \frac{1}{1+z},$$

and the coefficient of z^n is

$$\frac{1}{18}n2^n + \frac{11}{54}2^n + \frac{2}{9}n(-1)^n + \frac{8}{27}(-1)^n.$$

4. Ternary Smirnov Words Starting and Ending With the Letter 0 – Counting the Letters 1

In a very similar way we can count the total number of occurrences of the letter 1. A second variable u is counting the numbers 1:

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z, u) &= z + zu f_1(z, u) + z f_2(z, u), \\ f_1(z, u) &= z f_0(z, u) + z f_2(z, u), \\ f_2(z, u) &= z f_0(z) + z u f_1(z, u). \end{aligned}$$

We find, for instance,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u} f_0(z, 1) = \frac{1}{18} \frac{1}{(1-2z)^2} - \frac{7}{54} \frac{1}{1-2z} - \frac{1}{9} \frac{1}{(1+z)^2} + \frac{5}{27} \frac{1}{1+z}$$

and the coefficient of z^n is

$$\frac{1}{18} n 2^n - \frac{2}{27} 2^n - \frac{1}{9} n (-1)^n + \frac{2}{27} (-1)^n.$$

Other results are similar.

5. Words Interpreted as Decimal (and Other) Numbers

Let $q \geq 3$ be a base, and define $\text{value}(x_1 \dots x_n) = x_1 q^{n-1} + x_2 q^{n-2} + \dots + x_n$. As in [3], we consider S_n , the sum over the values of all Smirnov words of length n , rendered by zeros. The recursion $\text{value}(x_1 \dots x_n) = q \text{value}(x_1 \dots x_{n-1}) + x_n$ is obvious.

We can set up the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z, u) &= z + z f_1(z, u^q) + z f_2(z, u^q), \\ f_1(z, u) &= z u f_0(z, u^q) + z u f_2(z, u^q), \\ f_2(z, u) &= z u^2 f_0(z, u^q) + z u^2 f_1(z, u^q). \end{aligned}$$

Then the coefficient of $z^n u^k$ in $f_i(z, u)$ is the number of Smirnov words ending in i , having length n and $\text{value} = k$. We are only aiming at the total value, so in other words we should differentiate $f_i(z, u)$ and evaluate it at $u = 1$. The evaluations of $f_i(z) := f_i(z, 1)$ have been given before, so, with $g_i(z) = \frac{\partial}{\partial u} f_i(z, 1)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} g_0(z) &= z + z g_1(z) + z g_2(z), \\ g_1(z) &= q z g_0(z) + q z g_2(z) + z f_0(z) + z f_2(z), \\ g_2(z) &= q z g_0(z) + q z g_1(z) + 2 z f_0(z) + 2 f_1(z). \end{aligned}$$

This system is readily solved, with result

$$g_0(z) = \frac{1}{2(q-1)(1+2q)(1-2qz)} - \frac{1}{(2+q)(q-1)(1+qz)} - \frac{q}{2(2+q)(q-1)(1-2z)} + \frac{q}{(q-1)(1+2q)(1+z)}.$$

Reading off the coefficient of z^n leads to the numbers S_n :

$$S_n = \frac{1}{2(q-1)(1+2q)} 2^n q^n - \frac{1}{(2+q)(q-1)} (-1)^n q^n - \frac{q}{2(2+q)(q-1)} 2^n + \frac{q}{(q-1)(1+2q)} (-1)^n.$$

Of course, the coefficients of $g_1(z)$ and $g_2(z)$ could also be determined, as well as higher moments, by more differentiations. We are not doing this here; we just want to indicate how things could be done efficiently.

The values for $q = 3$ are derived in [3] using long computations.

6. Inversions

An inversion (in a Smirnov word as always in this paper) is a pair $x_i > x_j$ and $1 \leq i < j \leq n$. To count the total number of inversions, we proceed as follows. We consider a *marked* letter i , so that the word can be written as $x = wiy$, and we count the inversions with first letter i . They are given by the number of symbols $< i$ in y . So the generating functions decompose:

$$\frac{1}{z} f_0(z) f_0(z) + \frac{1}{z} f_1(z) g_1(z, u) + \frac{1}{z} f_2(z) h_2(z, u).$$

The first factor refers to the words wi (ending at i), the second factor to the reversed word $y^R i$, where in $g_1(z, u)$ the second variable is used to count the letters 0, and in $h_2(z, u)$ the second variable is used to count the letters 0 or 1. Since the designated letter i is part of both factors, we must divide by z .

Now we have again

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(z) &= z + z f_1(z) + z f_2(z), \\ f_1(z) &= z f_0(z) + z f_2(z), \\ f_2(z) &= z f_0(z) + z f_1(z) \end{aligned}$$

and also

$$\begin{aligned} g_0(z, u) &= zu + z u g_1(z, u) + z u g_2(z, u), \\ g_1(z, u) &= z g_0(z, u) + z g_2(z, u), \\ g_2(z, u) &= z g_0(z, u) + z g_1(z, u) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} h_0(z, u) &= zu + zuh_1(z, u) + zuh_2(z, u), \\ h_1(z, u) &= zuh_0(z, u) + zuh_2(z, u), \\ h_2(z, u) &= zh_0(z, u) + zh_1(z, u). \end{aligned}$$

These systems are readily solved, and we only give the final answer:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \left(\frac{1}{z} f_0(z) f_0(z) + \frac{1}{z} f_1(z) g_1(z, u) + \frac{1}{z} f_2(z) h_2(z, u) \right) \Big|_{u=1} \\ = \frac{1}{18} \frac{1}{(1-2z)^3} - \frac{5}{54} \frac{1}{(1-2z)^2} + \frac{1}{9} \frac{1}{(1+z)^3} + \frac{4}{27} \frac{1}{(1+z)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

The coefficient of z^n in this is routinely found to be

$$\left(\frac{n^2}{36} - \frac{n}{108} - \frac{1}{27} \right) 2^n - \left(\frac{n^2}{18} + \frac{n}{54} - \frac{1}{27} \right) (-1)^n.$$

This formula was derived in [3] with significantly more effort.

7. Conclusion

The methods described here allow for all kinds of more refined results; we don't have space here to present more calculations.

The restriction to ternary words and first/last letter being 0 is superficial and could easily be replaced by larger alphabets and different conditions on the letters.

Calculations were done by Maple; they are easy to reproduce by the reader using any computer algebra system.

References

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